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DETERMINATION OF PARASITIC CONTAMINATION OF FRESH VEGETABLES AND FRUITS SOLD IN OPEN MARKET IN PLATEAU STATE: PUBLIC HEALTH THREAT.

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ABSTRACT

*Intestinal parasitic diseases are often a leading cause of illnesses in humans resulting in significant morbidity and mortality. There have been many reports related to a food borne illness linked to consuming of fresh vegetables and fruits, especially in developing countries. The study was designed to assess the parasitic contamination level of vegetables and fruits sold in open markets in Building Materials, and Kugiya in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State. 160 fresh vegetables and 160 fresh fruits were purchased randomly from the two markets and brought to the microbiology laboratory, Plateau State Polytechnic for parasitological analysis. Samples were washed in saline solution, followed by sedimentation for 24 hours. After that the supernatant was decanted leaving the sediment. The sediment was then transferred to a centrifuged at 300 revolution per minutes for five minutes. The supernatant was decanted and the sediment was transferred on a clean grease free slide cover with cover slip; mount on a microscope and examined using 10x and 40x objectives for the identification of ova, cyst or trophozoite of parasites. Result: The identified helminthes and protozans encountered were *Ascaris Lumbricoides*, Hookworm SPP, *Trichuris trichiuria*, *Hymelopsis nana*, *Giardia lamblia*, *Taenia SPP*, *Schistosomo mansoni*, *Strongyloides stercoralis* and *Entamoeba histolytica*. The most presominate parasites encountered was *Ascaris lumbricoides* 16(28.57%), hookworms SPP 8(14.28%), *Trichuris trichiuria* 7(12.5%), *Giardia lamblia* and *Strongycoides stercoralis* 6 (10.71%), *Taenia spp* 5 (8.92%) with less in *Hymolepis nana* and *Entamoeba histolytica* yst 2 (3.57%) respectively. The finding of this study evidenced that consumption of raw and unwashed vegetables and fruits possess great public health threat due to parasitic contamination. Therefore, it is important that health authorities in Plateau State create more awareness on the needs to always wash vegetables and fruits thoroughly before consumption.*

KEYWORDS: vegetable and fruits, contamination, intestinal parasites, public health threat

INTRODUCTION

Fresh vegetables and fruits are highly beneficial to man and as potential source of vitamin, dietary fibres, mineral salts, proteins, and antioxidant are commonly used in almost all the societies in the world including Plateau State (Kkanet *et al.*, 2020, Gufom 2022). Routine consumption of fresh vegetables and fruits such as tomato, spinach, cabbage, lettuce, cucumber, carrot, green pepper, green beans, peas, onion, ginger, garlic, waterleaf, bitter leaf, okra, potato, pumpkin, lady finger, mango, guava, banana, orange, watermelon, pawpaw, coconut, pineapples, and apple has increased in Africa as a major source of nutrients rich in essential components helps in maintaining the body by providing nutrients, regulate body weight and preventing some conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, stroke, hypertension, diabetes, and cataracts. (Khan *et al.*, 2020).

Despite these numerous health benefits of vegetables and fruits to man, it has been established that they served as vehicles for the transmission food borne diseases (Khan *et al.*, 2020, Gufom *et al.*, 2022, Tefera *et al.*, 2014, Ajitha *et al.*, 2020). Vegetables/fruits are potential sources of several infections as they can become contaminated with different type of pathogenic agents such as parasites, enteric bacterial and viral when insufficiently washed, undercooked or uncooked before eating. Also, Abubakar *et al.*, (2020) reported that using untreated water, manure with sewage for irrigation or during cultivation could lead to high contamination rates of vegetables with Helminthes ova and protozoan cyst. Other factors like lack of proper hand washing during prayers and other religious activities practices, poor sewage disposal facilities, use of untreated human and animals faeces manure, improper harvest methods, unhygienic handling conditions during storage, transportation and preparation could lead to parasitic contamination of vegetables and fruits resulting in food borne diseases to humans (Terefe *et al.*, 2024, Ajitha *et al.*, 2020, Gufom, 2022). Most times, infection can be acquired through preventable attitude of keeping contamination unwashed fingers by food handlers and vendors circulating currency, insects and winds during dry season (Akom, 2017).

3.5 billion persons has been reported infected with intestinal parasite worldwide and 450 million are at risks of intestinal parasite infections, with an estimated 200,000 deaths annually (Khan *et al.*, 2020). Soil transmitted helminthes like *Ascaris lumbricoides* infect over one billion people, *Trichuris trichiuria* 79 million and hookworms (*ancylostoma duodenale* and *necator americanus*) 740 million persons with children as the most venerable (Khan *et al.*, 2020). Studies in different part of the world have implicated that ingestion of parasitological contaminated vegetables is a major health risk factor for the alarming rates of intestinal parasites infection and food borne diseases (Akoma *et al.*, 2017).

Epidemiological studies indicated that there is an increase in the prevalence of food borne infections which are mostly associated with fresh vegetables. It is also estimated that 200,000 deaths occur due to parasitic infections in developing countries with about 300 million experiencing severe illness (Abubakar *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, some studies were carried out to determine the transmission of pathogens intestinal parasite in fresh vegetables in some cities such as Akum in Ethiopia, Khartum in Sudan, Beriha in Egypt, Hawo/Vianarim Misorata Libya, Dahmarcity in Libya, Yemen, Jordan, Ghana, Cameroon, Turkey, Jos Plateau, Azare in Bauchi in Nigeria, Triuchirappalli South India. The results in all these researches showed a distinctive levels of vegetables and fruits implication due to low sanitation and hygiene which make it vulnerable to intestinal parasites (Kiros & Gebre Cherkes 2012 cited in Gufom *et al.*, 2022).

Public health impact of consuming contaminated vegetables with these pathogens can contribute to malnutrition, iron deficiency, anaemia, cognitive malfunction, diarrhea, stunting growth in children, morbidity, tissue reaction such as granuloma and provoking intestinal obstruction or rectal prolapsed and it can also cause significant economic lost (Auta *et al.*, 2017).

Considering the public health implications, it is important to determine whether the available and daily handled and consumed fresh vegetables and fruits commonly obtained from the open market are contaminated with these intestinal parasites of medical important. Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate the prevalence of intestinal parasitic contamination and their possibility of association with vegetables and fruits eaten raw and unwashed in Jos Plateau State Middle Belt, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Area**

The study was carried out in building materials market and Kugiya market in Jos South Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria about 15 kilometers South East of Jos, the State Capital covers a total of 512km², it lies between latitude (9°34'22' and 9°54'40') N of equator and longitude (8⁰, 39'55') and (8⁰,59'13') E of the meridian, and with an average altitude of about 1280m above sea level. The National Population Census projected figure of the area was 407, 9500 as March 2016. The human population density of the area stand at 778 inhabitants 1km². It has a cool climatic condition known as mountain climatic due to its altitude November to February is normally the peak of cold period whereas March and April are warm period (Bala *et al.*, 2021).

- **Period of the Study**

The present study was carried out from February 2025 to November 2025 to ascertain the level of parasite contamination of fresh vegetables and fruits sold in the two markets in Jos South Local Government Area, Plateau State, Middle Belt, Nigeria.

- **Sample Collection**

The samples were purchased from February 2025 to November 2025, eight (8) types of vegetables and fruits including onion, tomatoes, lettuce, carrot, cucumber, African spinach, cabbage, green pepper, guava, coconut, orange, pineapples, watermelon, apple, banana and pawpaw. Equal number of samples (20 each) total three hundred and twenty (320) were purchased randomly and put in a clear plastic bag properly labeled, and brought to microbiology laboratory, main campus of Plateau State Polytechnic Barkin Ladi for parasitological analysis.

A portion of 200g of each vegetable and fruit was washed separately in 100ml of normal saline for detaching stage of the parasites such as ova, larva and cysts or trophozoite, helminths, air protozoans, parasite commonly assumed to be associated with vegetables and fruits contamination. After overnight sedimentation washing solution; 15ml of the sediment was transferred to a centrifuge test tube using sieve to remove undesirable matters or debris accordingly.

For concentrating the parasite stages, the tube was centrifuged at 3000rpm for five (5) minutes (Terfera *et al.*, 2014 in Gufom *et. al.*, 2025). After centrifugation, the supernatant was decanted carefully without shaking the sediment agitated gently by hand for careful redistribution the parasitic stages (ova or cyst). Finally, the sediments were transferred to a clean grease free slide, cover with cover slip, mount on microscope and examined using 10x and 40x objective. The parasites ova and cyst were identified based on their morphological detail described by Arora and Arora 2008, 2012 cited in Gufom *et. al.*, 2022, Ajitha *et. al.*, 2020).

RESULTS

A total of three hundred and twenty samples which comprises of one hundred and sixty (160) fresh vegetables and one hundred and sixty (160) fresh fruits were purchased from some selected open air markets and examined for parasitic contamination using standard parasitological techniques (Arora & Arora 2008, 2012 cited in Gufom *et al.*, 2022). The outcome of the laboratory examination was analyzed and presented in tables accordingly.

The results revealed that 56 (35%) vegetables and 34 (21.25%) fruits samples identified to be contaminated with pathogenic intestinal parasite as showed in table (1) one in the studied area.

Table 2 shows the prevalence of parasite on each of the selected vegetables analysed for intestinal parasite contamination. The results indicated that among the vegetables selected and examined for the parasites contamination, carrot had the highest 12 (7.5%), followed by onion 10 (6.25%) and cabbage 10 (6.25%) lettuce 8 (5%), cucumber 6 (3.75%), the lowest in green pepper 4 (3.5%) with no contamination in African spinach.

Table 3 indicated the distribution of pathogenic intestinal parasite amongst the selected fruits in the study. Of the fruits examined, almost 34% were contaminated with different parasites species. Guava has 12 (7.5%), watermelon 8 (5%), coconut 6 (3.75%), banana and pawpaw 4 (2.5%) each with less in apple 2 (1.25%) while no contamination was observed in orange and pineapple respectively. Table 4 indicates the frequency of occurrence of intestinal parasite ova and cysts encountered in the vegetables was *Ascaris lumbricoides* 16(28.57%), *Hookworm spp* 8(14.28%), *Trichuris trichiuria*, *Giardia lamblia spp* and *Strongyloides stercoralis* 6 (10.71%). *Taenia spp* 5 (8.42%), *hymenolepis nana* 2(3.57%) which is the least while *E. histolytica* cysts in protozoan group has 2 (3.57%).

In table 5, it is observed that the frequency of the occurrences of the individual intestinal parasites in the various fruits selected for this research. The ova and cyst of intestinal parasitic were encountered as observed in table 4 above. *Ascaris lumbricoides* is the most prevalent as high as 10(29.41%), *Hookworm spp* 6(17.64%), *Trichuris trichiuria* and *Taenia* 3(8.82%), *Hymenolepis nana* 4 (11.76%), *Giardia lamblia*, *Schistosoma mansoni*, *Strongyloides stercoralis* 2(3.88%), *Entamoeba histolytica* and coli 1(1.94%) respectively.

Table 1: Parasite contamination of fresh vegetables, fruits in the study area

Items	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
Vegetables	160	56	35
Fruits	160	34	21.25
Total	320	70	28.13

Table 2: Distribution of Parasites on the Vegetables in the Study Area

Items	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
Onion	20	10	6.25
Lettuce	20	8	5
Carrot	20	12	7.5
Cucumber	20	6	3.75
African spinach	20	0	0.00
Cabbage	20	10	6.25
Tomato	20	6	3.75
Green pepper	20	4	2.5
Total	160	56	35

Table 3: Distribution of Parasites on the Fruits in the Study Area

Items	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
Guava	20	12	7.5
Coconut	20	6	3.75
Orange	20	0	0.00
Pineapples	20	0	0.00
Watermelon	20	8	5
Apple	20	2	1.25
Banana	20	4	2.5
Pawpaw	20	4	2.5
Total	160	34	28.13

Table 3: Frequency of Occurrence of Parasites Ova and Cyst in Vegetables in the Studied Area

Items	Frequency	Prevalence (%)
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	16	28.57
<i>Hookworm spp</i>	8	14.28
<i>Trichuris trichiuria</i>	7	12.5
<i>Hypmenolepis nana</i>	2	3.57
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	6	10.71
<i>Taenia spp</i>	5	8.92
<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	4	7.14
<i>Stongyloide stercoralis</i>	6	10.71
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	2	3.57
Total	56	100

Table 4: Frequency of Occurrence of Parasites Ova and Cyst in Fruits in the Studied Area

Items	Frequency	Prevalence (%)
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	10	29.41
<i>Hookworm spp</i>	6	17.64
<i>Trichuris trichiuria</i>	3	8.82
<i>Hypmenolepis nana</i>	4	11.76
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	2	5.88
<i>Taenia spp</i>	3	8.82
<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	2	5.88
<i>Stongyloide stercoralis</i>	2	5.88
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	1	1.94
Total	34	100

DISCUSSION

The detection of human intestinal parasitic stages from some selected fresh vegetables and fruits in this study is an indicative of faecal contamination of humans or animal origin. As intestinal parasites are widely distributed not only due to the favorable climatic condition that support the survival or dissemination of the parasites but also due to the poor/unhygienic sanitary condition that facilitate faecal pollution of soil environment, water, crops and food stuff (Dawet et. al., 2019).

The present study has attempted to assess the level of contamination and prevalence of different selected fresh vegetables and fruits sold in Building Material and Kugiya Market in Jos South Local Government

Area. Infestation of fresh vegetables and fruits with human pathogenic species of parasites ova and cyst revealed that out of three hundred and twenty (320) samples. In eight (8) varieties of some selected vegetables and fruits examined, 90 (28.13%) of the samples were contaminated. The results in this research supported the findings Dawet et. al., (2019). Ajitha et. al., (2020) reported parasitic contamination of 41.85% in Jos Plateau and 19.7% in Tiruchirappalli South India. Abubakar et. al., (2020) reported 23.43% in Katagumu Area of Bauchi State Nigeria and Flore et. al., (2025) reported 61.5% in produces in Bamenda Municap a city in North West region Cameron.

The results of the study obtained on 160 selected fresh vegetables and 160 fruits analyzed for intestinal parasitic contamination indicates that 56 (35%) vegetables and 34 (21.25%) fruits were contaminated with both helminths and protozoans as shown in table 1. The findings are in line with that of (Dawel et. al.; 2019, Ajitha et. al.; 2020, and Flore et.al.; 2025; Abubakar et. al.; 2020).

Table 2 shows the distribution of intestinal parasitic contamination of fresh vegetables in the study area with carrot as the highest contamination with 12 (7.5%) followed by onion and cabbage 10 (6.3%), lettuce 8 (5%) cucumber and tomato 6 (3.5%) green pepper 4 (2.5%) with non-contamination on African Spinach. For fresh fruits as captured in table 3, indicated the prevalence occurrences of human pathogen intestinal parasitic contamination amongst six (6) selected fresh fruits as follows, guava 12 (7.5%), coconuts 3 (3.75%), banana and pawpaw had equal number of contaminations 4 (2.5%) accordingly with the lowest in apple as 2 (1.25%).

Table 4 shows the frequency occurrence of intestinal parasites ova and cyst and trophozites seven selected fresh vegetables. The results indicates that *Ascarislumbricoide* has 16 (28.57%), hookworm, spp 8 (14.28%), *Trichuris trichiura* 7 (12.5%), *Giardia lamblia* and *Strongyloide steracolis* had 6 (10.71%), *Taenia* spp 5 (8.92%), schistosome 4 (7.14%), *H. nana* and *Entameoba. histolytic* 2(2.57%) is similar to findings of Gufom et. al.; 2022). The frequency occurrence of intestinal parasites ova and cyst and trophozites in fruits as indicated in table 5. The results obtained showed that *Ascarislumbricoide* has 10 (29.41%), hookworm, spp 6 (17.64%), *Trichuris trichiura* 7 and *Taenia* spp 3(5.82%), *Giardia lamblia* *Schistosome mansoni* and *strongyloides steracolis* 2(5.88%), while *Entamoeba histolytica* and *coli* had 1 (1.94%). This findings in line with that of Zeynudunet. al.; 2025).

The habits of eating unwashed vegetables and fruits is commonly practiced in the study area. Hence, the findings of the study present a public health threat, which required intervention to prevent transmission of human's pathogenic parasitic disease that can be acquired through consumption of contaminated vegetables and fruits. Therefore, proper washing and disinfecting of vegetables and fruits is very important. (Istifanus & Panda 2018 cited in Gufom et. al.; 2022).

However, recommended the immersion in water containing active calcium hydrochloride for 30 minutes for preventing of the parasitic illness

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, selected fresh vegetables and fruits contaminated with human pathogens intestinal parasites were identifies. The most frequent detected parasitic form was in particular *Ascaris lumbricoide*, *Hookworms*, *Trichuris trichiura*, ova, and *histolytica* cyst both in vegetables and fruits. Carrots and guava were amongst the most contaminated selected fresh vegetables and fruits screened for parasites and fruits screened for parasite ova and cysts. The contamination of vegetables and fruits with pathogenic parasites poses health risk to consumers if consume without proper cleaning or cooking.

• **Recommendation**

Based on the findings of this study, the following were outlined as recommendations:

1. A comprehensive health education should be given to farmers, vendor and the general public on the health risk factors associated with consumption of raw and unwashed or improper washing of vegetables and fruits before eating.
2. Reduction risk of human intestinal pathogenic parasitic associated with vegetables and fruits can be better achieved through control of faecal pollution in the farm during harvesting, transportation, distribution or retail market or in the home.
3. Organic manure, sewage system should be treated or sterilize before use for the cultivation of crops.
4. The need for the improvement of sanitation facilities in the market where vegetables, fruits and other crops are sold.
5. Government or market management authorities should make provision for adequate and safe water for washing vegetables/fruits and farm produce.
6. Vendor should also avoid the contact of vegetables with solid dust while displaying for sale so as to prevent the transmission of pathogenic parasitic.

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